

Content-based Processing for Masking Minimization in Multi-track Recordings

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Abstract

An important task in music post-production is masking minimization. When minimizing masking, an audio engineer carefully crafts each instrument's sound into the audible spectrum and the stereo panorama. This is done in order to achieve an intelligible sonic mixture in which the intended role of each instrument can be clearly appreciated by the listener. As with the rest of the post-production chain, masking minimization is a task where both technology and creativity co-exist in equal proportions. This means that there is not a single right way of approaching the problem, but rather every engineer will have its own approach and personal taste. Nevertheless, based on the assumption that one possible approach to music post-production is entirely rule-based, recent research has been concentrated on the topic of Automatic Mixing of Music, focusing on areas such as automatic equalization, automatic stereo panning and automatic gain-control. Given that Masking minimization is a crucial aspect of multi-track down-mixing, this thesis is concerned with developing an intelligent audio system that is able to automatically minimize masking between the different acoustic sources that comprise a musical mix. Because auditory masking is a perceptual phenomenon, the system makes use of a computational model of perception to transform the audio signals into a perceptual domain. In this domain, masking can be detected and quantified. From this analysis stage, the processing parameters to minimize unwanted masking are obtained. The processing stage consists of an adaptive filter-bank that is able to equalize the tracks in a time-varying fashion. Because of the subjective nature of the results, a subjective test is performed in order to find the system parameters that result in positive evaluations from the listeners in an attempt to further understand the phenomenon of auditory masking in a musical context.

To my parents...

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1

Introduction

1.1 Motivation

Post-production of music is typically concerned with the processing of the individual acoustic sources that comprise a musical piece. This is done to achieve a balanced and interesting sonic mixture that is pleasing to the listener. Traditionally up until recent years, post-production was carried out in professional facilities by qualified engineers using expensive hardware equipment. Advancements in digital signal processing then allowed the replacement of these expensive units by their cost-friendly software counterparts. Since then, a growing trend of personal studios and self-produced musicians came about and the demand for more intuitive and user-friendly software has been increasing ever since. Even though there are still many debates on the matter of analog vs. digital processing audio quality, the advantage of the digital world in terms of flexibility, possibilities and cost is obvious. At the same time, computational models of music cognition and audio analysis have been receiving a lot of academic attention. These models allow computers to understand music like humans do (to some extent) and so they open the door for a new class of audio processing algorithms, which process the audio based on the content of the sound. Some examples of this are Content-based transformations [14] and Adaptive Digital Audio Effects [7]. Additionally, the idea of automatic mixing of music is also currently being worked on. The main idea behind this is that various different intelligent audio processing effects can be put together that tackle individual issues of the music mixing task, like automatic equalization, automatic panning, and automatic gain control[2,3,4]. It is then the intention of this

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thesis to put together an intelligent audio processor that minimizes masking automatically and as such is a step towards the bigger goal of automatic mixing of music as well as a useful post-production tool. The motivation behind this system comes from the fact that recording and post-production equipment is now more accessible to musicians. Because of this fact many musicians are now self-produced, but because their technical knowledge may not be the same as that of a professional audio engineer, the need for intelligent software arises, software that is able to operate on a higher level of abstraction than traditional processing methods.

1.2 Masking within a musical context

When mixing a song, most of the decisions of an audio engineer are influenced by context; the genre of the music, the intended audience and for all we know even the weather at the time of mixing can influence an engineer's decisions. Nevertheless there is one aspect of a mix that is crucial and for which most audio engineers share the same view. This is masking. Masking has been defined as the process by which the threshold of audibility for one sound is raised by the presence of another (masking) sound. Also, as the amount by which the threshold of audibility of a sound is raised by the presence of another (masking) sound [6]. This can be illustrated in figure 1.1.

However, when talking in terms of a musical mix, the term attains a quite different definition, namely; when one signal competes with another, reducing the hearing systems ability to fully hear the desired signal, masking has occurred [5]. The latter definition emphasizes the fact that in a multi-track mix several instruments are fighting to be heard, so the ability to fully hear every individual instrument is reduced but in most cases all of the instruments are still audible. As long as the sounds of different instruments are mixed together to form a musical piece, they will inevitably overlap each other in frequency and time. Some of this overlap is unavoidable and necessary but some of it can be detrimental to the overall quality of the mix. This is because excess of this overlap results in a mix that lacks definition as the musical nuances of each instrument cannot be fully appreciated. Accordingly, when there is a lot of masking going on between the different tracks of a multi-track recording, the resulting mix is cloudy and confusing. On the other hand, an unmasked mix is the one where all the instruments are clearly defined thus allowing the listener to fully appreciate their intended role in

Figure 1.1: Masking pattern for narrow band of noise masker centered at 410 Hz - Each curve shows the elevation of the hearing threshold of a sinusoidal tone as a function of the frequency of the tone. The level of the masker is indicated at the top of each curve

the music. As such, it is the authors opinion that masking minimization should be one of the pillars of an automatic mixing system. In figure 1.2 we can visualize the effective frequency ranges of common musical instruments, it is easy to observe that most of them heavily overlap in frequency, the idea behind masking minimization is to craft the different mix ingredients into the frequency spectrum so that they don't interfere with each other. It turns out that panning the sources apart also minimizes masking between them, but given that the work in this thesis is only concerned with content-based equalization this fact is not taken into account by the system, this could be a good area for improvement in the future.

In his book [21], Roey Izhaki has put together an interesting set of subjective terms that are commonly linked to a deficiency or excess of energy in a certain frequency band. In the case of frequency masking, when the energies of various instruments overlap in a given band, an excess of energy will most probably originate in that band. Depending on the frequency band, the listener will associate that excess of energy to a negative

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sensation. Figure 1.3 shows these subjective terms associated with different frequency bands across the audible spectrum. This implies that when minimizing masking, the system should try to reduce the excess of energy in a given band without creating a deficiency in that band.

1.3 Research Goals

This section is concerned with presenting the goals of this research. The first question to be answered is whether unwanted masking (within a musical context) can be quantified and robustly detected using a computational approach. After that, the next important question to answer is how to dynamically equalize the signals to reduce masking without introducing artifacts or other audible consequences. Finally, it will be explored to what extent masking needs to be reduced in order for the mix to have a positive evaluation from listeners in an attempt to gain a deeper understanding of what masking means in a musical context. More specifically The goals of this research are the following:

- To implement a computational model of masking within a musical context. The model should be able to detect and quantify the regions of masking between the different tracks of a multi-track recording.
- To implement a content-based processing system that is able to automatically minimize masking between these tracks by modifying their spectral content across time.
- To validate the results of the system with a subjective test and to determine the optimal parameters of the system that result in positive evaluations from the listeners.

It is important to mention that there is a special case of masking minimization that applies to lead vocals and solo instruments. It is assumed that these are commonly the most important instruments in a song and therefore they should be unmasked from the rest of the mixture as much as possible. For this reason when dealing with lead vocals or solo instruments the system has the ability to receive user input in which a track is prioritized and thus it gives priority to these type of tracks.

Figure 1.2: An abstraction of the frequency content and its distribution in a musical piece - (a) An imbalanced frequency distribution where some instruments overlap and some areas are left unoccupied. (b) A balanced frequency distribution where the instruments do not overlap and together comprise a full frequency spectrum. (c) The real frequency ranges of common musical instruments.

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Figure 1.3: Subjective terminology associated with different frequency bands
- Each region is associated with a different auditory sensation, the excess or deficiency of energy in a given band is associated with a negative sensation

1.4 Thesis Outline

The rest of this thesis is organized as follows: Chapter 2 presents the relevant scientific background behind this work (the reader is encouraged to read this chapter before moving on to subsequent chapters). Chapter 3 presents the state of the art in issues directly or indirectly related to this work. Chapter 4 presents the computational model of masking between the different acoustic sources that comprise a musical piece. Chapter 5 presents the content-based processing scheme used to minimize masking in the musical piece. Chapter 6 presents the subjective evaluation. Conclusions and future work considerations are discussed in Chapter 7.

1. INTRODUCTION

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Scientific Background

This Chapter is concerned with presenting the scientific background behind this work. As mentioned before, the content-based processing audio system in this work has both an analysis stage and a processing stage. The analysis stage is mainly based on a psychoacoustic model of human perception of sound and the processing stage is based on Short-time Fourier Transform analysis re-synthesis. It is then the aim of this chapter to present important scientific concepts about these two fundamental blocks of this work.

2.1 Psychoacoustics

The field of auditory perception, or psychoacoustics, studies the way humans perceive sound. One of the main goals of these studies is to find relationships between the characteristics of the sound that enter the ear and the sensations that they produce. Within the field there are several topics, like: the physics of sound, the physiology of the auditory system, frequency selectivity and masking, pitch perception, loudness perception, temporal analysis, sound localization, and the perceptual organization of complex auditory scenes are some examples. For this work, we make use of some information about frequency selectivity and masking in the auditory system, therefore some key concepts about this are presented below. Most of the concepts introduced here are based on the work of Brian Moore [1].

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2.1.1 The Power Spectrum Model of Masking

In his book, Brian Moore defines masking in the following two ways:

- The process by which the threshold of audibility for one sound is raised by the presence of another (masking) sound.
- The amount by which the threshold of audibility of a sound is raised by the presence of another (masking) sound. The unit customarily used is the decibel.

As early as the beginning of the 1900's scientists had already shown that a signal is most easily masked by a sound having frequency components close to those of the signal (or the same as those of the signal). This led to the idea that our ability to separate the components of a complex sound depends, at least in part, on the frequency resolving power of the basilar membrane. It is also believed that masking denotes the limits of frequency selectivity, or put another way, when the selectivity of our ear is insufficient to separate the signal and the masker, then masking occurs [1]. Harvey Fletcher was one of the first scientists to study masking. One of his famous experiments consisted of measuring the hearing threshold of a signal as a function of the bandwidth of a bandpass noise masker. The noise was always centered at the signals frequency and the power density of the noise was held constant. He found that the threshold of the signal tends to increase with noise bandwidth until a given bandwidth and then the threshold becomes constant. To explain these results he suggested that the auditory system behaves like a filter-bank with overlapping filters, these are now referred to as "auditory filters". It turns out that modern experiments also support this point of view. In brief, the power spectrum model of masking says that when trying to listen to a signal in the presence of noise, a listener will use a filter with a center frequency close to that of the signal, so this means that the signal is passed and a lot of the noise is removed, it is also assumed that the threshold of the signal is determined by the signal-to-noise ratio in the output of the filter. These set of assumptions is known as the Power Spectrum Model of Masking and it is the basis for the sections that come next.

2.1.2 Auditory Filters and Critical Bands

Many experiments have been designed to “measure” the shape of the auditory filters. For detail on these experiments the reader is encouraged to read [1]. Briefly, the auditory filters have been found to have a shape similar to a rounded exponential function but it has also been determined that the filters are not shape invariant. This means that they change their response as a function of their input level, with their lower frequency slope becoming less steep as the input to the filter increases. This variation in shape is illustrated in figure 2.1. It has also been found experimentally that the bandwidth of the auditory filters increases as a function of their centre frequency. Figure 2.2 shows the results of several experiments in which the equivalent rectangular bandwidth of the auditory filters are calculated as a function of the filter’s centre frequency. The work in this thesis makes use of the ERB scale proposed by Moore and Glasberg, which is represented by the solid black line in the figure. The ERB scale is given by the following equation, (where F is the centre frequency in KHz):

$$ERB = 24.7(4.37F + 1) \tag{2.1}$$

2.1.3 Excitogram and Masking Threshold

An excitogram is a time-frequency representation of a sound which is meant to correspond to the amount of neural activity that is evoked by a stimulus over time [8]. The excitogram is also known as a cochleagram and it is obtained by calculating the output energy of each auditory filter as a function of the filter’s centre frequency over time. Put another way, the excitogram is obtained by calculating the excitation pattern of a sound in a frame-wise manner assuming that the sound is stationary in each frame. Figure 2.3 illustrates the process of calculating the excitation pattern of a sound. The excitation pattern has been found to be highly correlated to the masking audiograms like the one shown in figure 1.1. This means that the excitation pattern can be used as a means of detecting masking between sounds. In fact, many perceptual audio coders make use of an excitation pattern, or a variation of it, to find areas in which the artifacts of compression will not be perceived by human listeners [6]. These areas are delimited by the masking threshold which is illustrated in figure 2.4.

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Figure 2.1: Shape of the auditory filter - This figure illustrates the variation in the response of the auditory filter with centre frequency 1 KHz as the input to the filter increases from 20 to 90 dB SPL. It can be seen that the lower frequency slope becomes less steep as the input to the filter increases

Figure 2.2: Auditory filter bandwidth - This figure illustrates the results of several experiments designed to measure the bandwidth of the auditory filters. The solid black line denotes the ERB scale which will be used in the rest of this work

Figure 2.3: Excitation pattern calculation - The upper image shows the auditory filters and the lower image shows the derived excitation pattern. The excitation pattern evoked by a 1kHz tone is derived by calculating the output of different auditory filters (a through e). The tone is represented with a dotted line. Note that the excitation pattern is not symmetric, showing a tendency towards the higher frequencies. This is caused by the increasing bandwidth of the auditory filters as well as their non-symmetrical shape (the lower frequency slope being less steep) and is an important fact when modeling masking

2. SCIENTIFIC BACKGROUND

Figure 2.4: Masking threshold - This image shows the masking threshold evoked by a strong sinusoidal masker. The shape of the masking threshold is very correlated to the shape of the excitation pattern but it is shifted vertically by some amount. It has been found that the sounds that fall entirely within the masking threshold are not audible

2.2 Analysis/Re-synthesis with the STFT

The auditory system functions as a spectrum analyzer, detecting the frequencies that make up the incoming sound over time. This is mostly done at the cochlea, where the basilar membrane works like a set of overlapping band-pass filters. Spectral representations are so widely used in sound applications because they mimic the behavior of the ear [22]. An important spectral representation is the Fourier representation, which has been studied extensively and has applications in many scientific fields. A method for analysis/synthesis of time-varying signals, that is based on a Fourier representation, is reviewed in this section. Namely, the short-time Fourier transform, which is used in this work as a means of filtering the audio tracks in a time-varying fashion as well as in the calculation of the Excitograms. The first step towards understanding the STFT technique is to study the Fourier transform.

2.2.1 The Discrete Fourier Transform

The Fourier transform allows the decomposition of a time domain waveform into a set of sinusoidal components by computing the projection of the signal with several complex exponentials of different frequencies. The most common definition of the transform is

in its continuous form. Because we are dealing with digitalized audio signals we will present the discrete version of the Fourier transform which is known as the Discrete Fourier transform (DFT):

$$X(k) = \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} x(n)e^{-j\omega_k n}, \quad \omega_k = 2\pi k/N, k = 0, 1, \dots, N-1 \quad (2.2)$$

In the equation above, k represents the number of sinusoidal components that will be used to decompose the time domain signal. These are also known as frequency bins. As you can see, k is the same as the length of the signal, this infers that the signal is bandlimited as it has a finite length. The complex exponentials $e^{-j\omega_k n}$ are the different sinusoids, in the form of rotating vectors at different speeds (radians per sample), which correspond to the different frequencies that will be “tested”. $X(k)$ contains a complex vector that contains information about “how much” of each of the sinusoids is present in the signal, as well as the phases of the sinusoids, this is referred to as a complex spectrum. To convert radian frequency (ω) into frequency in Hz (f) the following relation is used:

$$f = f_s \omega / 2\pi \quad (2.3)$$

where f_s is the sampling rate. It is possible to invert this representation and as such transform a complex $X(k)$ spectrum into a time domain waveform. This is achieved with the inverse DFT that has the following definition:

$$x(n) = 1/N \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} X(k)e^{j\omega_k n} \quad (2.4)$$

One of the reasons why the DFT is used so much is because of a fast implementation of it. The FFT, or fast fourier transform allows the computation of the complex spectrum to be computationally effective. The traditional implementation of the FFT requires the length of the signal, N , to be a power of 2. By making this restriction the computation time is reduced from one proportional to N^2 for the DFT to one proportional to $N \log N$ for the FFT [22].

2.2.2 The Short-time Fourier transform

Because musical sounds are time-varying the DFT is not appropriate for analyzing them. A solution to this problem is to analyze short pieces of the sound in which the

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sound can be considered stationary. In order to do this the sound is broken up into consecutive frames using a windowing function. The mathematical definition of the STFT is given below:

$$X_l(k) = \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} w(n)x(n + lH)e^{-j\omega_k n} \quad (2.5)$$

where l is the frame number, H is the time advance of the window, also known as hop size, and w is the windowing function. The STFT returns a set of complex spectra, one for each frame of the signal under analysis. The role of the windowing function is to select a portion of the signal but also, as it tapers the ends of the analyzed data, it converts the frequency spectrum into a smooth function. The choice of windowing function, hop size and the computation of the DFT are important parameters when calculating the STFT. A good review of how to properly select these parameters can be found in [22]. The relevance of using the STFT in this work is that it allows us to manipulate the frequency content of a sound across time. This is done by converting the complex spectra into its magnitude and phase parts, manipulating the magnitude part and then applying the inverse STFT with the original phase to obtain the transformed audio. In order to obtain the magnitude and phase from the complex data we make use of the following relations:

$$magnitude = |X(k)| = \sqrt{a(k)^2 + b(k)^2} \quad (2.6)$$

$$phase = \angle X(k) = \tan^{-1}[b(k)/a(k)] \quad (in\ radians) \quad (2.7)$$

Where a and b represent the real and imaginary parts of the complex data respectively.

$$a(k) = \Re\{X_l(k)\} \quad (2.8)$$

$$b(k) = \Im\{X_l(k)\} \quad (2.9)$$

When inverting the STFT, the inverse DFT of each frame is calculated and the results are added together as the window advances in time. When the value of H is the same as the one used in the analysis stage, the inverse STFT will result in an identity property. But it is important to consider the effect of the window overlap. Because the overlap of the windowing function will not add up to a constant value in most cases, it is required to undo the effect of this overlap in order to avoid an amplitude modulation in the

2.2 Analysis/Re-synthesis with the STFT

re-synthesized signal. When the process is being done off-line, it is possible to calculate the envelope that is produced by the overlap of the windows and then multiply the re-synthesized signal by the inverse of this envelope to undo the effect. Figure 2.5 shows the amplitude modulation that results from a kaiser window of length M with different hop sizes.

Figure 2.5: Amplitude modulation due to window overlap - This figure illustrates the amplitude modulation introduced by the overlap of the kaiser window function of length M . Panel (a) shows the envelope for $H = M/2$. Panel (b) shows the envelope for $H = M/4$, taken from [22]

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Figure 2.6: Kaiser window - Kaiser window function responsible for the amplitude modulation displayed in figure 2.5, where $M = 1024$ samples and $\beta = 2.5$

3

Content-based Equalization of Multi-track Recordings: The State of the Art

3.1 Introduction

The topic of Content-based Processing of audio is a fairly new one, thus there is no established academic tradition for it. Despite this fact, and the lack of an accepted theoretical framework, there have been some recent investigations in this area that have shown promising results. Automatic Equalization in the context of Automatic Mixing, which is by definition a Content-based process, has been attempted by Enrique Perez Gonzalez and Joshua Reiss from the Centre for Digital Music in Queen Mary University of London. They have shown that it is possible to spectrally unmask one track from the rest of the mix by cross-adaptive methods (by taking into account all tracks, not just the input to the system). They also found that minimization of masking between the different tracks of a mix can be achieved to some extent by using spectral modification (EQ), with all the EQ parameters being derived automatically. Their work will be discussed with detail later on. Aside from the groundbreaking work by Perez and Reiss there is a great amount of literature on topics that are somehow related to Content-based Equalization and that give room for improvement to the current approaches. Dale Reed proposed a perceptual assistant to do sound equalization based on inductive learning and K-NN pattern recognition, his work will also be discussed with

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more detail below. Also, starting from the work that has been done in Adaptive Digital Audio Effects (where the effects are controlled by features extracted from the sound itself) to the area of Psychoacoustics, there are many past contributions that open the door for achieving a higher level, more flexible and more perceptually meaningful type of Content-based Equalization than the ones achieved so far. The goal of this chapter is to introduce the reader to such contributions. The work by Perez, Reiss and Reed will be reviewed first. Then, a study that showed how a computer is able to identify the most perceptually relevant frequencies of a sound will be discussed; this type of information would clearly benefit a Content-based equalization system. After this, the work by Verfaillie on Adaptive Audio Effects and the work of Amatriain and Bonada on Content-based transformations will be reviewed, as it is believed that it is relevant material. Finally, a framework for processing audio in a perceptual domain is introduced. This framework will be adopted by the CBEQ system presented in this thesis. Note that an introduction to Psychoacoustic concepts like Critical Bands, Auditory Filters, Excitation Patterns and Masking can be found in the Scientific Background chapter of this thesis. All of the concepts introduced there play an important role in this work, so the reader is encouraged to carefully review them before moving on to subsequent chapters.

3.2 Masking Minimization: a Cross-adaptive approach

Perez and Reiss implemented a digital audio effect for real-time mixing applications in which a track is enhanced with respect to the other tracks in terms of its perceived predominance and clarity [3]. This type of effect seems perfect for lead vocals and solo instruments. The resulting mix is the direct result of the analysis of the content of each individual track. In this work, a mix of audio tracks (Ch_n) is defined to be the following:

$$mix = \sum_{n=1}^N Ch_n(t) \quad (3.1)$$

A cross-adaptive process applied to any given channel would depend on the features extracted from all of the individual channels by a given feature retrieval algorithm

3.2 Masking Minimization: a Cross-adaptive approach

(FRA). After such process is applied to every channel in the mix, a new processed mix is obtained:

$$mix_{fx} = \sum_{n=1}^N fx_n(Ch_n, fv_1, fv_2, \dots, fv_x) \quad (3.2)$$

In equation 2, the applied effect function (fx) takes the input channel as a parameter along with the feature vectors of all the individual channels (fv_x). It is clear from this equation that the content of all the tracks affect the processing of each individual track. A quite simplistic measure of masking is then defined to be the amount of overlap between the track of interest (Ch_m) and the rest of the mix.

$$SM = (FFT\{Ch_m\})^2 - (FFT\{mix - Ch_m\})^2 \quad (3.3)$$

Where $SM > 0$ means that the track is spectrally unmasked from the rest of the mix and $SM < 0$ indicates the opposite. Then, in order to take the temporal evolution of the track into account, equation 3 is performed in a frame-wise manner.

$$ASM = \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} SM_t \quad (3.4)$$

The Accumulated Spectral Masking of a source (ASM) is then a measurement of masking over-time. This measure is only used to test the algorithm and it does not influence the signal processing stage. In order to unmask the user-selected channel from the rest of the mixture, the authors propose to use a full range magnitude adjustment instead of traditional equalization. More specifically, they have chosen to lower the levels of the other channels in proportion to their spectral relationship to the user-selected channel. The feature that controls this process is the Accumulated Spectral Decomposition (ASD). The ASD algorithm categorizes each input track into a spectral class k_n , which contains information about its spectral content (the higher the value of k_n , the higher the overall frequency content of the track). The algorithm is composed of a filter bank of N bands (where N is the same as the number of tracks). The input track is decomposed into these N bands every 1 ms and the filter responsible for the highest output is chosen as the k value (k ranges from 1 to N). This means that most of the energy of the analyzed sound lives in the chosen filters frequency range and thus the sound can be described by it. It should be clear from the above explanation that

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Figure 3.1: ASD Filter-bank magnitude response - The Magnitude response of the filter-bank is showed for $N = 8$. The input track is decomposed into these N bands every 1 ms and the filter responsible for the highest output is chosen as the k value (k ranges from 1 to N).

the resolution of the spectral decomposition (and therefore the resolution of the value of k) is dependant on the number of tracks. This is a limitation of this system, as the algorithm will only work the same for different multi-track recordings when their number of tracks is the same. The next stage in the Masking Minimization algorithm is the mapping between the features (k_n) and the control parameter of the Cross-Adaptive Effect, which in this case is a simple gain stage. The idea is to apply the greatest attenuation to tracks that have similar spectral content to the user-selected track (Ch_m) and the least attenuation to the tracks with different spectral content. This is best illustrated in figure 3.2. An analytical expression of the Gaussian mapping function along with the details of its derivation can be found in [3]. To summarize, this Cross-adaptive audio effect is able to unmask a user-selected track by adaptively attenuating the rest of the channels in proportion to their spectral relation with this user-selected track. A general expression for this system is then:

$$mix_g(t) = \sum_{n=1}^N G_n Ch_n(t) \quad (3.5)$$

Where G_n are the gains that are applied to the tracks Ch_n . Note that the value of G is equal to 1 for $n=m$ which is the user selected track. The inputs to the algorithm are the following:

1. *Total number of tracks*: all of the recorded tracks to be mixed.
2. *Selection of a master track*: the track that will be enhanced.

Figure 3.2: Gaussian-like frequency dependent attenuation - In the above figure we can see a Gaussian-like gain function. The 8 vertical lines represent the possible values of k . In this specific case when $k=5$ (counting from left to right) the input track at this particular time (Ch_n) will be attenuated the most (-16 dB). This means that the user-selected track (Ch_m) must also have a value of $k=5$. In figure 3.1 this would correspond to a frequency around 700 Hz. The gain of Ch_m is left unchanged.

3. *Attenuation*: The maximum attenuation that will be applied.
4. *Q*: Corresponds to the quality factor of the Gaussian function, this value determines the spread of the attenuation towards neighboring values of k_m .

It is important to note that this method works better than the simpler method of just attenuating all tracks except the master track. If we do this, we would actually be attenuating some sounds that are not really masking the master track, in the other hand, by using this method we make sure that we attenuate only what we need to.

3.3 Automatic Equalization of Multi-Channel Audio

A method for automatically equalizing a multi-track mix was also proposed by Perez and Reiss [2]. Their approach attempts to achieve equal average perceptual loudness in all the frequency bands of each track. The method assumes that a mixture in which loudness per band tends to the overall average loudness of the signal is a well-equalized mixture with optimal inter-channel equalization intelligibility.

The proposed system comprises two fundamental parts, a cross-analysis block and a signal-processing block. The cross-analysis block is responsible for feeding the equaliza-

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tion parameters G_{km} to the signal-processing block, which is made up of an equalizer with fixed frequency bands. The analysis block makes use of a flat frequency response filter-bank to decompose each track into K frequency bands and for each band there is a corresponding equalizer band in the processing side, therefore the accuracy of the overall system is heavily dependent on the number of bands in the filter-bank. After a given track has been decomposed into K frequency bands the time-varying loudness of each band is calculated. The method for calculating the loudness values consists of a look up table search driven by an SPL measurement. The SPL measurement can either be acquired by a measurement microphone at the mixing position or can be a fixed value. The ISO 226 standard loudness contours are used as the look up table. The exact details of the method for calculating the loudness values are not specified, only that the loudness is averaged over time segments to obtain the time-varying loudness estimate l_{akm} where k denotes the band number and m the track number. For the sake of completeness and for the readers information, a robust method for calculating time-varying loudness has been proposed in [17]. The time-varying loudness is then passed through an adaptive noise-gate in order to remove any noisy parts of the signal. The next step deals with calculating a loudness value that is representative of the spectral band. This is done by accumulating the normalized histogram of l_{akm} in order to determine the mass probability function, and choosing the peak value $lp_{km}(n)$, which should correspond to the most probable loudness value in that band. After the lp values have been calculated for each band it is possible to calculate the average loudness of all channel equalization bands $L(n)$:

$$L(n) = \sum_{m=1}^M \left(\sum_{k=1}^K lp_{km}(n)/K \right) / M \quad (3.6)$$

Where M is the total number of tracks and K is the total number of frequency bands. After this value has been calculated it can be used to calculate the equalization parameters that are fed to the processing side. The equalization parameters are simply the gains G_{km} that are applied to each pre-determined fixed frequency bands. Again, for each band in the filter-bank decomposition there is a corresponding equalization band. This is illustrated below. Note that in the bottom plot the bands can either be boosted or attenuated depending on the values of G_{km} .

3.3 Automatic Equalization of Multi-Channel Audio

Figure 3.3: Analysis filter-bank and Equalizer bands - The top panel shows the analysis filter-bank and the bottom panel shows the corresponding equalizer bands.

Given that the equalization is attempting to achieve an equal average loudness across frequency bands of all tracks, the ratio of L and lp_{km} should be equal to one, meaning that the loudness in any given band for any given track should be the same as the average loudness L described above. So, to make sure this happens the gains G_{km} are calculated as follows:

$$G_{km}(n) = \frac{L(n)}{lp_{km}(n)} \quad (3.7)$$

The gains for each band are calculated and fed to the equalizer shown in figure 3 so that the signals are processed accordingly. As stated in [2] the system was not subjectively evaluated. Also, the system only seemed to work with high SPL input levels but this was due to implementation issues, in theory the proposed system should perform its task. This suggests that there is room for improvement and future work.

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3.4 A perceptual Assistant to do Equalization

As already mentioned, this system was not meant to perform fully automatic equalization but to serve as an assistant to the inexperienced engineer [18]. It works in the following way, a user inputs a sound to the equalizer and specifies a desired goal, the possible goals are the following: increase brightness, increase darkness, or increase smoothness. Then, based on a set of features that are extracted from the input sound, the equalizer finds a set of sound examples (previously stored in its memory) that are similar to the input sound with the same equalization goal. Based on the examples the system finds the proper EQ parameters to achieve the specified goal. This is an example of a system that uses inductive learning to acquire expert skill, and then the skill is used in a context dependent fashion. Basically, this system models the process that goes inside an Audio Engineers head. That is, the sound stimulus is perceived and the engineer recognizes the context. Then, based on a desired goal, the engineer remembers (either from education or past experience) and infers the proper equalization controls to achieve the desired goal. All of these steps are illustrated in figure 3.4. Every individual step of this process has a corresponding step in the intelligent equalization system. The context is acquired by extracting features from the sound, the goal is an input from the user, the memory is acquired from a training stage, the inference parameters are acquired by averaging the example parameters found in memory and the modification is then performed with the parameters derived from this inference stage. In order for the system to find the right examples in its memory it takes the input sound to an n -dimensional space (where n is the number of scalar features) and finds its closest neighbors. These closest neighbors correspond to sounds that are very similar to the input sound and have the same equalization goal; therefore it makes sense to apply a similar equalization to the one that was previously applied to these stored examples. To obtain a memory database, the system was trained with a total of 17 subjects (all of them sound reinforcement professionals or music students) and 41 sound segments. This gives 697 examples for each of the equalizer goals, and a total of 2091 examples. The users were asked to equalize a given sound to match a specified goal, and the following information was stored in memory for each user, for each of the sound-goal combinations:

3.4 A perceptual Assistant to do Equalization

- Sound file name
- Goal (one of 3 possibilities)
- Audio features extracted from that sound
- Final slider positions

Figure 3.4: Process of obtaining EQ parameters - Every individual step of this process has a corresponding step in the intelligent equalization system.

The Final Slider Positions correspond to the different band gains of the equalizer; a fixed total of 9 bands were used. The Audio Features that were extracted were the energy per each of these bands. Given that the sound files were all sampled at 22.05 KHz the 9 bands were distributed logarithmically into the range 0 - 11 KHz, which is enough resolution for most inexperienced users. Once all of these examples are stored in memory, the system is ready to be used. In order to test the system, a testing phase was designed. Only 11 subjects were selected to test the equalizer based on a listening test that determined their ability to discern equalization changes (the best 11 were chosen). The subjects were asked to listen to three equalized versions of a sound

3. CONTENT-BASED EQUALIZATION OF MULTI-TRACK RECORDINGS: THE STATE OF THE ART

example and choose which one of them was able to achieve one of the specified goals more accurately. The three equalized versions used different EQ parameters, derived in the following ways:

1. A linear average: obtained by averaging the equalization parameters of all 41 sounds for the given goal.
2. The NN average: obtained by averaging the equalization parameters of the 2 nearest neighbors from that users training database.
3. No change: no equalization (the sound is left unchanged).

The evaluation ranged from 1 to 15, where 1 means the equalization is not able to achieve the goal and 15 means that the equalization achieves the goal. Obviously, the users did not know which of the versions they were hearing and the order was randomized. The mean evaluation for the no change equalization was 2, for the linear average was 6, and for the NN average was 10. This means that the NN average type of equalization was over 68% better than the linear case and it was preferred 81% of the time. To summarize, the system proposed by Reed is meant to be used by an inexperienced user that wishes to perform equalization. The user only inputs a sound and selects the type of EQ. The system then analyzes the sound and finds a set of examples in its memory (using K-NN) that resemble the current example. From these examples the system finds the equalization parameters (in the form of band gains) to be applied to the input sound. The parameters are found by averaging the parameters of the stored examples. This system is a good example of content-based equalization and it proves that this type of EQ does offer an advantage over traditional EQ when aimed at inexperienced users.

3.5 Automatic Detection of Salient Frequencies

This work by Joerg Bitzer and Jay LeBoeuf presents several techniques to find the most significant frequencies in recorded audio tracks [19]. To evaluate the results, the list of detected frequencies is compared with a list of reported salient frequencies put together by several audio engineers. The results show that automatic detection is a possibility. It is important to remember that the definition of the most significant frequencies

3.5 Automatic Detection of Salient Frequencies

is entirely subjective, however, when several audio engineers have reported the same frequencies then we can conclude that there must be some kind of cue that makes the detected frequencies special, probably the frequencies that seem to impact the timbre of the sound the most. A previous contribution by the same authors examined the engineers agreement on salient frequencies and found out that such regions exist [16]. In this study there was an average of 2 obvious frequencies per sound file (obvious refers to the fact that all audio engineers reported these same frequencies). It is clear that an automatically generated list of salient frequencies would benefit an equalizer system. Such list could be used in several ways to model the creativity of an engineer, as this creativity seems to be driven by the perception of the salient frequencies anyways.

As a first step the reported frequencies are compared to a long term average spectrum of the sounds and it turns out that most of the frequencies are clearly visible as resonances (local maxima), therefore the algorithms presented aim to find these resonances. The first approach for detecting the resonances comes from a speech processing background. Namely, the LPC model. This model is able to approximate the spectral envelope of a sound and as such it is able to find the areas of resonance. In speech, these resonances are known as formants. It turns out that the angles of the complex roots of the LPC model give the values of the resonances. However, when the resonances found by the LPC are compared to the reported salient frequencies there doesnt seem to be an agreement. This is because the resolution of the LPC model is too broad. This is illustrated below. One other method uses the Welch Periodogram instead of the LPC model. Some heuristics are also introduced in order to improve results. Normally, the reported frequencies are local maxima, not global maxima. This means that if the ten most prominent frequencies in the periodogram are chosen for the list they would probably not correspond to the local maxima because they would all be at low frequencies. This happens because of the decreasing slope in the spectrum of most musical instruments. In order to overcome this issue, the detected maxima are weighted by their frequency in order to emphasize higher frequencies for the ranking in the list. Another heuristic introduced consists of only allowing one maximum per octave with an overlap of half an octave. With these rules the results improve. Figure 3.6 shows the results after applying the heuristics.

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Figure 3.5: Illustration of the LPC method - The blue line is the spectrum of the sound and the red dashed lines are the LPC model. The grey vertical lines are the frequencies detected by the LPC method and the black vertical lines are the reported frequencies. It is clear that this method does not give good results, as only one frequency seems to agree.

Figure 3.6: Welch Periodogram method - The gray vertical lines correspond the detected maxima. The grey horizontal lines correspond to the values after the weighting by frequency. The black vertical lines are the reported frequencies for this sound and the Power Spectral Density (Welch Periodogram) is shown in blue. The black horizontal lines show the search range. As you can see, this method detected frequencies close to the reported frequencies, if a tolerance value is introduced it can be said that all of the reported frequencies are detected in the example above when the list of detected frequencies is around ten entries and the FFT size used to calculate the periodogram is large enough (eg. $N=16384$).

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Some variations of the method include using the LPC model with the heuristics mentioned above and also using a warped LPC model to increase the resolution at lower frequencies. When more heuristics are applied the results improve even more. The improved heuristics deal with the frequency weighting (since the simple $1/f$ model does not fit all instruments) and with the way the algorithm detects local maxima. For a detailed description of the improved heuristics see [19]. All of the different methods (LPC, warped LPC, Welch Periodogram with heuristics + improved heuristics) were tested with 16 audio files of different instruments of length 20 seconds. The results are displayed in the figure below.

Figure 3.7: Results of different methods - The plot above shows the Length of the salient frequency list vs. detection ratio for several algorithms. The detection ratio ranges from 0 to 1, with a value of one indicating the detection of all the reported frequencies (within a tolerance bandwidth). The black solid line \diamond = Random detection (this is used as control). The black dashed line \triangleleft = RT (which is a musically meaningful random detection). The black dash-dotted line \circ = LPCr (root based LPC). The black dotted line ∇ = LPCs (LPC with heuristics). The light grey solid line $+$ = MW2k (Welch Periodogram with $N=2048$), and the light grey dashed line \square = MW16k (Welch Periodogram with $N=16384$). The light grey dotted line \triangleright = WLPC (Warped LPC) and the light grey dotted line \star = MWH (Welch Periodogram with improved heuristics). The best results are obtained with the Welch Periodogram method using a large value of N and applying heuristics.

To summarize, this contribution presents several methods to detect the salient frequencies of a sound. The results show that if we include lots of a-priori knowledge, in the form of heuristics, an algorithm can detect the salient frequencies with an accuracy of a one-third octave and with a list of just eight entries. It would be interesting to investigate the possibilities of applying this information in a content-based equalization system.

3.6 A-DAFX and Content-based Transformations

Even though the kinds of effects and transformations that will be discussed next are not directly linked with the topic of content-based processing for masking minimization, they form the basis for the class of intelligent processing algorithms in which the system in this work was based. The discussion that follows is not meant to go into detail of specific audio effects and transformations, instead it focuses on giving a general overview.

3.6.1 Adaptive Digital Audio Effects

Verfaille introduced a new class of Digital Audio effects which he named Adaptive Effects (A-DAFX). The main idea is that contrary to traditional audio effects, that are applied with the same control value for the whole sound, the adaptive effects are controlled with features extracted from the sound itself [7,15]. This type of effect needs both a feature extraction stage and a mapping from features to control values. The main idea behind this new class of effects is to give life to sounds, allowing to re-interpret the input sounds with a great coherence in the resulting sound. An existing type of adaptive effect is the compressor, which is based on the dynamic properties of the input sound. In this contribution however, the authors have generalized adaptive effects to those based on the spectral properties of the input signal. A general overview of A-DAFX is shown in figure 3.8. This type of system is closely linked with the perceptual assistant discussed in section 2.4, where the input from the user would be the specification of an EQ goal (see section 3.4). The actual set of features to be extracted depends on the application. For example, in section 3.4 the effect was equalization, so in that case it makes sense that the features were the energies of different frequency bands. In general, the idea is to have a set of time series of data that are able to describe the

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Figure 3.8: Genral overview of A-DAFX - The input signal $x(t)$ is analyzed and several features are extracted from it. These features are processed in some way in order to be mapped into effect control parameters (control values). The actual Digital Audio Effect receives the input signal and the control parameters from the mapping stage and processes the signal to achieve the modified sound. Note that the effect can also receive additional inputs from the user

temporal evolution of certain characteristics of the sound. For example, the spectral centroid, the RMS energy, amongst many others, can be used. A comprehensive review of audio descriptors can be found in [13]. Then in order to find a mapping between the time series of descriptors and the control values there must be an appropriate mapping process. Verfaillie introduced the concepts of connection type and connection law for this purpose. These will be explained next, along with a proposed method of mapping features to control parameters.

A connection between N features and M control parameters is said to be an N to M connection type. For example, a one to one connection is when one feature is used to control one effect parameter, such as the RMS energy controlling the amount of gain reduction in a compressor (although there are other parameters inputted by the user in this case). The connection law deals with the actual processing of the features, it can be a linear or non-linear process and there is one for each connection. In this work, the following mapping was proposed: Consider $k=3$ audio features, namely $F_k(t)$ for $t=1,NT$. The 3 features are combined in a linear way to yield one single time series. Prior to this linear combination the features are normalized between 0 and 1 and they are also weighted depending on their importance. In order to normalize the features the following max and min values are defined:

3.6 A-DAFX and Content-based Transformations

$$F_k^M = \max_{t \in [1:NT]} (|F_k(t)|) \quad (3.8)$$

$$F_k^m = \min_{t \in [1:NT]} (|F_k(t)|) \quad (3.9)$$

Then the features are combined as follows, where γ_k is the weight of the k^{th} feature:

$$F_g(t) = \frac{1}{\sum_k \gamma_k} \sum_k \gamma_k \frac{F_k(t) - F_k^m}{F_k^M - F_k^m} \quad (3.10)$$

After the k features have been combined there is a mapping according to a linear or non-linear mapping function. Verfaillie proposed the following types of mapping functions: linear, sinus, truncated and time stretched. They are all displayed in the figure below.

Figure 3.9: A-DAFX feature to control mapping functions - The input-output relationship of the proposed mappings is shown in the figure above. The final control curve is obtained after passing $F_g(t)$ through any of these functions.

The final step in the mapping process is the fitting of the control curve to the effect parameter boundaries. The mapped curved is fit between Δ_m (the minimum value of the effect parameter) and Δ_M , (the maximum value of the effect parameter).

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The effect parameter can be calculated as:

$$\Delta(t) = \Delta_m + (\Delta_M - \Delta_m)M(F_g(t)), \quad t = 1, \dots, NT \quad (3.11)$$

Where M is the mapping function.

3.6.2 Content-based Transformations

In this contribution the authors give a general framework for content-based transformations focusing on transformations that can change one of the main dimensions of the perceptual axis of sound [14]. These are: timbre, pitch, loudness, duration, position and quality. The authors present a spectral based analysis/synthesis approach to process signals and they explain how to extract features that can be used in the transformations in order to alter one of the main dimensions mentioned above without affecting the other ones. Even though the type of transformations addressed in this contribution are not motivated by masking minimization, the general framework that is presented is very related to the type of processing that is done by the work in this thesis. This framework is presented below.

Figure 3.10: Basic content-based processing overview - This figure show the basic framework of content-based transformations. An example of this type of processor is a compressor/limiter, where the parameters of the transformation are adapted to the content of the input signal

The first scenario that is presented is the one depicted in figure 3.10. In this case, the input sound undergoes an analysis stage, in which audio features are computed. Then, these features are used as a control to the transformation block. In this case the parameters of the transformation are dynamically adapted to the content of the input

3.6 A-DAFX and Content-based Transformations

signal [14]. An example of this kind of processing is a compressor/limiter, in this case the feature of the input signal that is commonly calculated is the RMS envelope or some other kind of energy measure. These type of features are calculated in the time domain. It has been determined that for *more interesting* transformations, the kind of features that are obtained from the time domain representation of the input signal may not be enough. This is because in a content-based transformation we want to be able to extract meaningful features from the analysis step and the time-segment processing is not well-suited for this sort of schemes. This is the case that applies to the work in this thesis. In particular, the analysis step should be able to yield more than just a set of features that act as control signals, this is why it becomes imperative to find a model for the signal in such a way that this intermediate representation is more suitable for applying some particular processes [14]. As we will see later, the model that was chosen for the masking minimization system is the cochleagram, or excitogram (see 2.1.3).

Figure 3.11: User interaction in content-based processing systems - The figure illustrates the ability of the user to interact with the system by supplying additional input in any stage of the process chain

Another important aspect of content-based transformations is discussed next. The idea of user interaction. Even in the simple case of a compressor/limiter mentioned above, the user input must be taken into account to set the threshold, compression ratio, etc. This is why a second scenario of content-based transformations is presented. This new scenario, depicted in figure 3.11, takes the interaction of the user into account.

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The user must be able to give input to the system at any of the stages in the processing chain. Either in the form of analysis parameters in the analysis stage, or in the form of additional control parameters for the effect, and even in the form of manipulating the feature-based control signals. These three cases are depicted in the figure above. As it will be shown in subsequent chapters, the user is allowed to interact with the masking minimization system by supplying input directly to the processing stage as well as to the analysis stage.

Interestingly, the authors of this contribution mentioned the use of a perceptual model in a content-based processing framework: “The computation cost and complexity of perceptual features does seldom pay for the increase of naturalness that can be gained in the transformation. A good mapping scheme is usually enough. Nevertheless, not many conclusions have been put forward on this area of perceptual adapted sound transformations and it is, surely, a field to invest efforts in the near future [14].” It is then another aim of this research to shed some light on this matter, although given the nature of the processing (masking minimization) it is the opinion of the author, that in this case, the use of perceptual features is indispensable.

3.7 Loudness Domain Signal Processing

Perhaps one of the most relevant contributions to the work in this thesis is the LDSP (Loudness Domain Signal Processing) framework introduced by Alan Seefeldt (9). The LDSP framework consists of transforming the audio into a perceptual representation using a psychoacoustic model of loudness perception. In this domain the signal is processed according to some desired transformation (automatic gain control and equalization are some of the possibilities) and then the model is inverted to obtain the processed audio. This is done because, as we know, the auditory system introduces some non-linearities that dictate the way we perceive sound. By processing the audio in a perceptual domain the idea is that *we actually perceive what we aimed for when processing the audio* as we are taking the response of the auditory system into account. As such this domain is ideal for processing tasks that are closely linked with our perception of sound. For this reason, masking minimization is a perfect task for which this kind of framework could be used. The first step of the model involves transforming

the audio into the loudness domain by means of a loudness model. Different loudness models are found in the literature, some of them are single band models (17) and some of them are multiple band (11). For the LDSP framework, a multiple band model is utilized. Figure 3.12 depicts the type of loudness model used. To process the audio in

Figure 3.12: Loudness model utilized by the LDSP framework - The audio is first filtered by the response of the outer/middle ear (transmission filter), then the audio is divided into critical bands by an auditory filter-bank, then the excitations are calculated. From these the specific loudness is obtained by making use of a non-linear transfer function. Finally, the result is integrated across bands to obtain a final loudness value

the loudness domain there is no need to integrate across bands. In fact, the processing is done in the specific loudness domain, where we have a kind of time-frequency representation $N(b, t)$ (where $b = \text{band}$, and $t = \text{time}$). In this case b is in units of ERB bands. To modify this specific loudness representation all we need to do is to multiply N by some transformation matrix $S(b, t)$ like follows:

$$\hat{N}[b, t] = \left(\prod_p S_p[b, t] \right) N[b, t] \quad (3.12)$$

A particular scaling S_p may be computed in any number of ways depending on the desired perceptual effect (9). In the case of masking minimization, it will be shown in Chapter 5 how this is done.

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Figure 3.13: Overview of the LDSP framework - This is an overview of the framework, the target specific loudness is obtained using equation 3.12

3.7.1 Inverting the model

The last step of the framework involves inverting the model in order to obtain the final processed audio. This is not a trivial task given that the auditory filter-bank is composed of overlapping bandpass filters which implies that if we alter only one of these filters, the neighbouring bands will also be affected. Given the importance of this stage, and the implications that it brings, it has been decided that the inversion of the model will be discussed with the details of its implementation in Chapter 5.

Figure 3.14: Auditory filter-bank magnitude response - This figure illustrates the response of the auditory filter-bank. The filters are spaced one ERB apart, starting from 50 Hz.

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4

Modeling masking within a musical context: Analysis Stage

This chapter is concerned with describing the process in which masking between tracks is detected and quantified. This is very important because if we are aiming at minimizing masking we must first be able to properly measure it. In brief, the steps that are followed to quantify masking are the following:

- Outer/Middle ear filtering: to account for the transmission of sound through the auditory channel.
- Gamma-tone filter-bank: to account for the resolution of the basilar membrane.
- Excitogram: a perceptual time-frequency representation of sound.
- Masking coefficient: to find areas of spectral overlap.
- Decision Function: to label sounds as either masker or maskee.
- Signal-to-masker ratio: to quantify the amount of masking between sounds.

The Signal to masker ratio (SMR) is the output of the analysis stage. In Chapter 5 we will see how the mapping of the analysis into the processing parameters is performed. Below, each of the stages in the analysis are explained.

4. MODELING MASKING WITHIN A MUSICAL CONTEXT: ANALYSIS STAGE

4.1 Outer/Middle ear filtering

In order to account for the transmission of the outer/middle ear we must filter the signal with an appropriate transfer function. The details of how this transfer function was experimentally determined are explained in [1]. Every track under analysis will be filtered by this response prior to the gamma-tone filter bank to account for the transmission of sound through the outer and middle ear channel. The filtering is performed in the frequency domain by multiplying the magnitude spectrum of each frame of audio with the response shown in figure 4.1. For the analysis, the audio is broken down into frames using a Blackman-Harris window of length 92 ms, which at a sample rate of 44.1 KHz amounts to 4096 samples. The hop size is set to half the window length and the FFT size is also 4096 samples.

Figure 4.1: Outer/Middle ear filtering - The magnitude response of the outer/middle ear

4.2 Gamma-tone filter-bank

We have discussed previously that the human auditory system behaves like a spectral analyzer, breaking up sounds into different frequency bands. This is mainly done in

the basilar membrane in the cochlea [1,20]. In Chapter 2 (Scientific Background) we have discussed the concept of auditory filters. These filters are responsible for the resolution of the spectral analysis. The second step of the analysis stage consists of a gamma-tone filter-bank decomposition of the tracks. The filter-bank is made up of 43 rounded exponential filters, with the first filter being located at $f_c = 50Hz$. and each filter being spaced one ERB apart (equation 2.1). The bandwidth of each filter also grows with equation 2.1. The magnitude response of this filter-bank is depicted in figure 4.2. After the outer/middle ear filtering, each frame of audio is multiplied with the response of each of the auditory filters, the energy at the output of each auditory filter is then calculated to form the excitation pattern. This means that the magnitude spectrum of a frame is multiplied with 43 different responses and for each of these multiplications there is one single scalar value (the output energy) that is calculated to form the excitogram.

Figure 4.2: Gamma-tone filter-bank - The magnitude response of the gamma-tone filter-bank. It is composed of 43 auditory filters each spaced one ERB apart, starting at $f_c = 50Hz$

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4.3 Excitogram

The excitogram is explained in section 2.1.3. As mentioned before, An excitogram is a time frequency representation of a sound which is meant to correspond to the amount of neural activity that is evoked by a stimulus over time [8,11]. The excitogram is also known as a cochleagram and it is obtained by calculating the output energy of each auditory filter as a function of the filters centre frequency, this done over time, one frame of audio at a time. Figure 4.3 depicts an excitogram of a sinusoidal tone with a frequency of 1 KHz. It is evident that the tone also excites frequencies close to 1kHz, and it seems to excite higher frequencies (above 1KHz) more than lower frequencies (below 1KHz). This is known as the upward spread of masking, which dictates that lower frequency components are able to mask higher frequency components more easily. The upward spread of masking is due to the increasing bandwidth of the auditory filters as well as the lower frequency slope being less steep (see section 2.1.2). For this reason the rounded exponential filters were modified to account for a high input level to the auditory filters (input level greater than 70 dB SPL). This is based on an assumption that an engineer mixes music at levels grater than 70 dB SPL and in fact most engineers mix at a level around 85 dB SPL. Figure 4.4 shows an example of a modified auditory filter. The shape of the filter is modified in the frequency domain, by simply adding values to the lower frequency slope in order to make it less steep.

4.4 Masking Coefficient

The next step in the model is the calculation of the masking coefficient. This is a number between 0 and 1 that corresponds to the amount of effective excitation overlap between two sounds. The masking coefcient between two excitations is given by the following equation:

$$MC(t, b) = 1 - \left(\frac{|e_1(t, b) - e_2(t, b)|}{60dB} \right) \quad (4.1)$$

Where e_1 and e_2 are the matrices containing the excitograms of each sound in decibels. The absolute value of the difference between the excitations is normalized with respect to 60 dB and then subtracted from one. As a result, when the excitograms have a similar value for a given ERB band and time, the MC is close to one. This specific case would yield a low signal-to-masker ratio in that band, as the auditory filter gets

Figure 4.3: Excitogram of 1 KHz tone - The excitogram of a steady 1 KHz tone is depicted above. The upward spread of masking can be clearly seen

Figure 4.4: Asymmetrical compensation - The response of the auditory filters is slightly modified to account for the input level, see section 2.1.2 for more information

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a similar amount of energy from both sounds, so this means that both sounds are heavily competing to be heard. As this is the definition of masking we have adopted (see Chapter 1) we call this descriptor the masking coefficient.

4.5 Decision Function

In order to calculate the signal-to-masker ratio we need to label each sound as a masker and the other one as the signal (maskee). The decision function makes this decision. It is best to explain the decision process with an example. Consider the sounds of a bass, a guitar strum and a cymbal. By listening to these you could tell where each sound should live in frequency, if the guitar was overlapping with the bass in the low frequencies you know you should attenuate the guitar to make room for the bass. In this case the guitar is the masker and the bass is the maskee. The decision function does the same thing ! It makes use of the sound's excitation centroid which is the center of gravity of the excitation of a sound. As such, the excitation centroid is able to give us some information about the nature of the sound, for example: the sound is a predominantly low frequency sound (bass), or the sound contains both low and high frequencies (guitar strum), or the sound is predominantly a high frequency sound (cymbal). When two sounds are overlapping in frequency the sound whose excitation centroid is closer to the area of overlapping is labelled as a maskee, and the other sound as a masker. Again, the excitation centroid descriptor is calculated in order to estimate the spectral region in which the sounds of the different tracks should live. For example, a bass should live well below a guitar and a guitar should live well below the cymbals, and this descriptor is able to give us this information. Based on this descriptor a decision is made like follows. For each of the time/frequency regions where the MC (Masking Coefficient) reveals masking, the following distances are calculated:

$$\Delta c_s = |b_t - EC_{t,s}| \quad (4.2)$$

Where b_t is the band where masking was detected (by the MC descriptor) at a given time t , s stands for *sound* and it can be either $s = 1$, for sound 1 or $s = 2$, for sound 2 (recall that we are measuring masking between two sounds only). $EC_{t,s}$ is the excitation centroid of track s at time t . From these values ($\Delta c_1, \Delta c_2$) we can figure out if the spectral region in which the sounds were competing is closer to the

centroid of either sound, which we are assuming is the region around which the sound should live. Therefore, the sound responsible for the smallest value of Δ is considered to be the maskee (the sound that is being masked), and the other sound is considered the masker. The excitation centroid EC is calculated for every frame of audio to form a time series. To calculate the centroid for one frame of audio we use the following equation:

$$EC = \frac{\sum_{b=1}^{43} bE(b)}{\sum_{b=1}^{43} E(b)} \quad (4.3)$$

Where b stands for ERB band and E for excitation value. In this way we obtain the center of gravity of the excitation vector for a single frame of audio. The last step of the decision function is to discard the values where the MC coefficient is less than a given MC threshold. This is done so that the user can interact with the system, by having the ability to change the "sensitivity" of the masking detection. Later on, we will illustrate the effect of the MC threshold with an example.

4.6 Signal-to-masker Ratio

Finally, now that the sounds have been labeled as masker/maskee, it is possible to calculate the signal-to-masker ratio at any auditory filter at any point in time. The SMR is then given by:

$$SMR_{t,b} = 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{E_{st,b}}{E_{mt,b}} \right) \quad (4.4)$$

Where E_s is the excitation of the maskee (protected signal) at time t and band b , and E_m is the excitation of the masker at time t and band b . This is the measure that is used to quantify masking between the different instruments, it is expressed in decibels.

To further illustrate the analysis process, an example will be shown. Two tracks are analyzed in order to find out where they mask each other. Track number one ($s = 1$) is an electric guitar riff played by Jimmy Page, and track number two ($s = 2$) is composed of Robert Plant's musical screams, it should be clear that it is an extract from a Led Zeppelin song. After the tracks are filtered by the outer/middle ear transfer function they are decomposed into 43 ERB bands. Then, their excitations are calculated as

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explained in figure 2.3 of the Scientific Background chapter. The excitations of these tracks are displayed in figures 4.5 and 4.6.

Figure 4.5: Excitogram of track 1 - The excitogram of a distorted electric guitar being played by Jimmy Page is shown

To calculate the decision function, we first calculate the excitation centroids for both sounds using equation 4.3. Then we use equation 4.2 to obtain the decision. The decision can be visualized in a time-frequency plot as can be seen in figure 4.7 and 4.8.

It should be clear that the effect of the MC threshold is that of adding sensitivity to the detection of masking. When the MC threshold is close to one, more values of the decision are discarded, the only values that remain are the ones located in the regions where the MC coefficient has a number bigger than the MC threshold, and because the MC coefficient ranges 0-1, only a few values are left. The SMR is the last step of the analysis stage and it is shown in figure 4.9 along with the instantaneous excitation to which it corresponds shown in figure 4.10.

Figure 4.6: Excitogram of track 2 - The excitogram of Robert Plant's musical screams is shown

Figure 4.7: Decision function with $MCth = 0.9$ - The decision for these tracks is shown. The areas in green have an index of 1 which means that track one is considered a maskee in these regions. The areas in red have an index of 2, which means that track two is considered a maskee in these regions. This decision was calculated with a MC threshold of 0.9

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Figure 4.8: Decision function with $MCth = 0.7$ - The decision for these tracks is shown. The areas in green have an index of 1 which means that track one is considered a maskee in these regions. The areas in red have an index of 2, which means that track two is considered a maskee in these regions. This decision was calculated with a MC threshold of 0.7

Figure 4.9: Instantaneous SMR for tracks 1 and 2 - The SMR is shown, when the SMR shows no value for a band it means that there was no masking detected at that band

Figure 4.10: Instantaneous excitations at $t = 1$ second - The instantaneous excitations from which the SMR in figure 4.9 was derived.

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After the analysis is complete the next stage of the system is the processing stage. In Chapter 5 we will see that in order to process two audio tracks, to minimize masking between them, the results of the analysis (the SMR values) have to be mapped into processing parameters, after this, the sounds are filtered by means of Short time fourier transform analysis-resynthesis using the parameters obtained in the mapping.

5

Content-based Masking Minimization Equalizer: Processing Stage

This chapter is concerned with presenting the mapping strategy used to map the results of the analysis into the processing parameters. Remember that the whole idea behind A-DAFX is that the processing of the audio is based on descriptors. In the case of masking minimization, the descriptor that is responsible for the processing is the SMR. The calculation of the SMR is explained in Chapter 4. Following is a detailed explanation of the mapping and processing schemes. The processing of the audio is also done in a frame-wise manner, the window size and hop size match those of the analysis stage although this does not always has to be the case. In the case that the analysis and processing stages required a different resolution it would then be required to interpolate the values appropriately.

5.1 Mapping: From SMR to Processing Parameters

Lets say we wanted to manipulate the SMR between sounds. This means we need to change their excitations as this is the main component in the calculation of the SMR (see equation 4.3). After changing the excitations we need to invert the perceptual model in order to obtain the corresponding audio waveform that is responsible for the new excitations, as we will explain this is not a trivial task, and only a partial solution

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to the problem was found.

5.1.1 Target excitations

Say we have an original excitation E_m belonging to a sound that was determined to be a masker in a given time frame and band. If we wanted to increase the SMR (which in turn reduces masking) we would need to attenuate the masking sound's excitation in that time frame and band. This attenuated excitation will be referred to as the target excitation. To obtain a target excitation we need to start with the definition of the SMR (equation 4.3) and solve for E_m given a desired SMR. The target excitation then becomes $E_t(t, b)$ instead of $E_m(t, b)$, which was the original excitation of the masker.

$$E_t(t, b) = \frac{E_s(t, b)}{10^{SMR/10}} \quad (5.1)$$

Once we have obtained the target excitation that would result in the desired SMR, we can calculate a set of scalings s (one per ERB band, 43 in total) that applied to E_m result in E_t . The scalings are calculated as follows:

$$s = \frac{E_t(b)}{E_m(b)} \quad (5.2)$$

Note that we have dropped the time index in equation 5.2, this is because from now on, the explanation is concerned with a single frame of audio, this of course has to be done for every frame. This means that s is a vector that has the scalings of the 43 ERB bands of a given frame. We would now think that in order to obtain the audio responsible for E_t we would have to scale the filters in the gamma-tone filter-bank with the scalings in s , and then pass the masker sound through the filter-bank to obtain E_t . The only problem is that we cannot manipulate the gains of the ERB bands that easily. This is because the filters that are used to calculate the excitation patterns overlap in frequency and this means that if we manipulate a given band by scaling it, the neighboring bands will be affected as well. Figure 5.1 Illustrates the overlapping that takes place between two consecutive filters, this kind of overlapping takes place no matter the center frequency of the filters, though the area of overlapping does vary across frequency. This can also be seen in figure 4.2.

5.1.2 Contribution Matrix

Because of this important fact the actual mapping strategy implemented is not as simple as simply scaling the filters in the gamma-tone filter-bank, instead the actual scalings that are applied to the filter-bank need to be obtained by taking the contribution amongst filters into account.

Figure 5.1: Contribution amongst filters in the Gamma-tone filter-bank - As you can see, the filters overlap in frequency, this means that scaling the gain of one filter will clearly affect the gain of the neighboring band.

In order to take this kind of overlapping into account we need to build a matrix A with the contribution amongst filters in the following way:

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & \cdots & a_{1n} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & \cdots & a_{2n} \\ \vdots & & \ddots & \vdots \\ a_{m1} & a_{m2} & \cdots & a_{mn} \end{bmatrix}$$

Where $m = n = 43$, one for each band in the gamma-tone filter-bank. The values of $a_{m,n}$ are obtained like follows:

$$a_{m,n} = \frac{\sum_k overlap_{m,n}(k)}{\sum_k H_m(k)} \quad (5.3)$$

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Where $overlap_{m,n}$ is the array containing the overlapping values between the auditory filters of bands m and n (the green line in figure 5.1), and $H_m(k)$ is the magnitude response of filter m . Using this definition of A we know that the total gain t of the filter-bank is obtained like follows:

$$t = Ag \tag{5.4}$$

Where g is the 43 element vector containing the gains of the individual filters. Equation 5.4 is saying that the total gain of the filter-bank is affected by the overlapping filters, usually every band will have a total gain higher than g as the neighboring bands also contribute to the total gain. With this in mind we can now understand why the initial solution of scaling the filters with the scalings s was not a proper solution. Instead we can let the total gain t equal the scalings s and solve for g . In this way we are finding the actual gains that when applied to each individual filter result in a total gain of s , solving for g we get:

$$g = A^{-1}s \tag{5.5}$$

Again, g is a 43 element vector containing the scalings (one per ERB band) that when used to scale the filters in the gamma-tone filter-bank, results in a frame of audio that will have an excitation similar to $E_t(b)$. The gain vector g has to be calculated for every frame.

5.1.3 Gain Matrix and Smoothing

By calculating a gain vector g for every frame of audio, we form the gain matrix $G(b, t)$, where the columns of G correspond to the ERB band number and the rows are the different time units (in units of analysis frames). As the processing is performed off-line, we have the possibility to smooth the gain matrix G prior to the equalization. As has been mentioned before, the gain vectors g are calculated across time to form the gain matrix $G(b, t)$. It turns out that abrupt changes in the gains amongst consecutive audio regions result in an audible artifact in the final processed audio. For this reason, the gain matrix $G(b, t)$ is smoothed across rows, which has the effect of smoothing the gain of each band across time. This is done using a simple moving average low pass filter :

$$G_{row}[t] = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{j=0}^{M-1} x[t+j] \quad (5.6)$$

By using a value of $M=5$ the artifacts are significantly reduced without drastically affecting the results of the SMR.

5.1.4 Synthesis filter normalization

An important fact to take into account when processing the audio is that if we want to provide a perfect reconstruction when all the gains of the auditory filters equal one we must normalize the filters in the gamma-tone filter-bank [9]. This is done in the following way:

$$N_b(k) = \frac{H_b(k)}{\sum_i H_i(k)} \quad (5.7)$$

Where $N_b(k)$ is the magnitude response of the normalized gamma-tone filter of band b , and $H_b(k)$ is the magnitude response of the original analysis filter at the same band. The filters in figure 5.1 have been normalized, hence the reason why their gains are not unity.

5.2 Processing: STFT Filtering

After the mapping stage comes the actual filtering of the audio. This is done in an analysis/resynthesis manner (see Chapter 2, section 2). In brief, the audio is broken down into frames with a windowing function, each frame of audio is multiplied with the magnitude response of each of the scaled gamma-tone filters and then summed together to form the the STFT of the processed audio $Y(k, t)$:

$$Y(k, t) = \left(\sum_b G(b, t) N_b(k) \right) X(k, t) \quad (5.8)$$

Where the columns of matrix G are the gain vectors g calculated across time, $N_b(k)$ is the magnitude response of the normalized auditory filter at band b , and $X(k, t)$ is the STFT of the original audio. The final step of the model inversion is to generate a time domain processed audio signal $y(t)$ through standard overlap-add synthesis of the STFT [22].

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5.3 User Interaction via GUI

The masking minimization system allows the interaction of the user via a graphical user interface. The user is allowed to give input in several stages of the process. Initially, the user is able to set the relative levels between the tracks prior to analysis. Further in the analysis stage the user is able to change the MC threshold (see section 4.5) to alter the "sensitivity" of the masking detection. Finally, in the processing stage, the user inputs the desired SMR. Another option to the user is that of prioritizing a track, this has the effect of bypassing the decision function as the prioritized track is always considered the maskee, as such, the non-prioritized track will be attenuated to attain the desired SMR.

Figure 5.2: Graphical user interface - The user is allowed to set the relative levels between tracks as well as manipulate the MC threshold and SMR parameters

6

Subjective Evaluation

One of the main goals of the research was to find the processing parameters that resulted in positive evaluations from the listeners in the hopes of getting to some conclusions about the phenomenon of masking within a musical context . In order to investigate this, a subjective evaluation was performed in which different versions of a mix of instruments is presented to a group of listeners (composed of audio engineers and musicians) and they have to decided which mix they prefer. There are two parts to the evaluation. Part 1 is concerned with pairs of instruments and the listener is asked two questions:

- 1. In which version can you listen to the individual instruments more clearly ?
- 2. Which version do you like the most ?

Part 2 is concerned with mixes composed of a vocal/solo track accompanied by a rest-of-the-instruments track (accompaniment), in this part the listener is asked two questions:

- 1. In which version can you listen to the voice/solo more clearly ?
- 2. Which version do you like the most ?

6.1 Evaluation Setup

The different versions of the mixes are composed of an original (not equalized) mix and a set of equalized versions using different values for the MCth and the SMR. The

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MCth takes on the values: 0.7, 0.8 and 0.9. The SMR takes on the values 5 dB, 10 dB, 20 dB. For a database of 5 different instrument mixes for each part, this results in 90 audio files. Given that the approximate length of each audio file is around 10 seconds the entire listening time is 15 minutes for each subject. To this, we add a 5 min break between parts, plus the response time, for a total evaluation duration of around 30 min per subject. A total of 8 different subjects were chosen to evaluate the system (all of them either audio engineers or studio musicians). The results of the evaluation are presented below.

6.2 Evaluation Results

6.2.1 Part 1

Part 1 is concerned with pairs of instruments. Only pair combinations of common instruments were chosen for the evaluation, including: guitar, bass, drums, synth, piano, and trumpet. The tables below show the results for the different questions. There were a total of 40 answers for each question (5 different mixes times 8 subjects). The percentage number of times that the given parameter combination was chosen as an answer to question 1 is shown in table 6.1, the same is true for question 2 in table 6.2.

Table 6.1: Part 1 - Question 1 (In which version can you listen to the individual instruments more clearly ?)

MCth	SMR=5dB	SMR=10dB	SMR=20dB	
7	5%	27.5%	10%	Original = 7.5%
8	0%	22.5%	17.5%	
9	2.5%	2.5%	5%	

Table 6.2: Part 1 - Question 2 (Which version do you like the most ?)

MCth	SMR=5dB	SMR=10dB	SMR=20dB	
7	10%	17.5%	5%	Original = 20%
8	7.5%	15%	5%	
9	15%	2.5%	2.5%	

6.2.2 Part 2

Part 2 is concerned with vocals and solo instruments. In this part of the evaluation the option of prioritizing a track is used (see section 5.3), giving priority to the vocal/solo parts in an attempt to make them stand out from the rest of the mix as much as possible. The tables below show the percentages of times that the given parameter combination was chosen as the answer to questions 1 and 2. The types of instruments that make up the accompaniment tracks for part 2 are the same as those mentioned in part 1, but the prioritized tracks are either, electric guitar, trumpet or vocals, which are common solo instruments.

Table 6.3: Part 2 - Question 1 (In which version can you listen to the vocals/solo more clearly ?)

MCth	SMR=5dB	SMR=10dB	SMR=20dB	
7	5%	27.5%	25%	original = 10%
8	0%	7.5%	10%	
9	12.5%	2.5%	0	

Table 6.4: Part 2 - Question 2 (Which version do you like the most ?)

MCth	SMR=5dB	SMR=10dB	SMR=20dB	
7	2.5%	17.5%	7.5%	original = 22.5%
8	2.5%	20%	5%	
9	10%	12.5%	0	

From these results we can make some conclusions about the parameters that result in positive evaluations. Chapter 7 is concerned with analyzing the results and sharing these conclusions.

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7

Discussion & Future Work

From the results presented in Chapter 6 we can draw some conclusions about masking within a musical context. First of all, we can observe that the answers for questions 1 and 2 returned quite different results. This suggests that masking is not the main factor for a listener when deciding which version he likes the most. Also, as we can see, the original version was the one with the highest score in question 2 for both cases, which at a first glance would seem discouraging. However, even though the listeners preferred the original version 20% of the time in part 1, this means that the listeners preferred some processed version 80% of the time. The same is true for part 2, the listeners preferred some processed version 77% of the time.

7.1 Part 1

Following is the analysis of the results for part 1. The two questions are analyzed separately and the findings are presented below.

7.1.1 Question 1

The value of the $MCth$ that resulted in most picks for question 1 was $MCth = 0.7$, with a total of 42.5% of the answers. Following is $MCth = 0.8$, with a total of 40% of the answers, after that comes $MCth = 0.9$ with 10% of the answers and finally, the original version with 7.5%. From these results we can conclude that a lower $MCth$ results in a more obvious masking reduction. In the case of the SMR, the value which resulted in the most answers was $SMR = 10dB$ with a total of 52.5% of the answers.

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Following is $SMR = 20dB$ with a total of 32.5% of the answers, after that comes $SMR = 5dB$ and the original both with a total of 7.5% of the answers. From these results we can conclude that 5 dB does not result in an obvious masking reduction, and that there is a clear difference between the original and the processed versions with higher SMR values ($SMR = 10dB$ and $SMR = 20dB$). Putting these two conclusions together we find that that an optimum set of parameters seems to be $MCth = 0.7$ and $SMR = 10dB$. This will of course vary between the different mixes depending on the instruments and relative levels, and it should only be taken as a reference.

7.1.2 Question 2

The value of the $MCth$ that resulted in most picks for question 1 was $MCth = 0.7$, with a total of 32.5% of the answers. Following is $MCth = 0.8$, with a total of 27.5% of the answers, after that comes $MCth = 0.9$ and the original both with 20% of the answers. From these results we can conclude that a lower $MCth$ results in a more positive evaluation. In the case of the SMR, the value which resulted in the most answers was $SMR = 10dB$ with a total of 35% of the answers. Following is $SMR = 5dB$ with a total of 32.5% of the answers, after that comes the original with 20% of the answers and finally $SMR = 20dB$ with a total of 12.5% of the answers. From these results we can conclude that a too high value of the SMR parameter does not result in a positive evaluation. Even though the original version is the one with the highest score, we can still see that the subjects chose some processed version 80% of the time, with the second most popular being the combination $MCth = 0.7$ and $SMR = 10dB$.

7.2 Part 2

Following is the analysis of the results for part 2. The two questions are analyzed separately and the findings are presented below.

7.2.1 Question 1

The value of the $MCth$ that resulted in most picks for question 1 was $MCth = 0.7$, with a total of 57.5% of the answers. Following is $MCth = 0.8$, with a total of 17.5% of the answers, after that comes $MCth = 0.9$ with 15% of the answers and finally, the original version with 10%. From these results we can conclude that a lower $MCth$ results in a

more obvious vocal/solo clarity. In the case of the SMR, the value which resulted in the most answers was $SMR = 10dB$ with a total of 37.5% of the answers. Following is $SMR = 20dB$ with a total of 35% of the answers, after that comes $SMR = 5dB$ with a total of 17.5% and finally the original with 10%. These results suggest that most of the subjects can listen to the vocals/solo more clearly when the SMR is greater than 5 dB. Putting these two conclusions together we find that the optimum parameters are $MCth=0.7$ and a SMR greater than 5 dB. Again, these are just reference values.

7.2.2 Question 2

The values of the $MCth$ that resulted in most picks for question 2 were $MCth = 0.7$ and $MCth = 0.8$, both with a total of 27.5% of the answers. Following are $MCth = 0.9$ and the original, both with a total of 22.5% of the answers. From these results we observe that the answers seem to be more evenly distributed, which suggests that the influence of the $MCth$ is not as crucial for this question. In the case of the SMR, the value which resulted in the most answers was $SMR = 10dB$ with a total of 50% of the answers. Following is $SMR = 5dB$ with a total of 15% of the answers, after that comes $SMR = 20dB$ with 12.5%, and the original with 22.5% of the answers. From these results we can conclude that even though the original version was picked the most, the users still picked a processed version around 77% of the time, and specifically the combinations of $MCth = 7and8$ with $SMR = 10dB$ are responsible for 37.5% of the picks. Even though we don't know all the reasons of why the subject likes a version the most, the results suggest that the reduction of masking does influence the decision in some cases.

7.3 Considerations and Future Work

As we can see, the parameters that returned more positive evaluations seems to be around 0.7 - 0.8 for the $MCth$ and around 10 dB for the SMR. Again, these are just reference values, and the user of the system is the final judge on what sounds good and what doesn't. It might be that a particular application calls for some parameter combination that would sound awful in another situation. In the end, it has been found that masking can be successfully minimized by the system and that the processing does seem to have a positive influence on the mixes in most cases. An important issue

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to have in mind is that when calculating the decision function (see section 4.5) the excitation centroid (EC) value might be the same for both sounds, this would return an error as no sound could be properly labelled. A possible solution to this problem is to use another descriptor other than the excitation centroid, like a weighted average of the position of the three most excited auditory filters (weighted by their excitation values). This would significantly reduce the probability of two sounds having the same descriptor values. Another important consideration is that in order to further minimize masking without affecting the spectral characteristics of the mix the stereo panorama can be used. This has not been taken into account in this work and it is assumed that the tracks that are processed will not be panned apart in the final mix. It would be interesting to add stereo unmasking to the system and to extend the evaluation in order to find appropriate parameters as a function of stereo separation. Finally, given that the system in this thesis is meant to contribute to the bigger goal of automatic mixing of music, it could be interesting to integrate it with some other existing methods [2,3,4,12] and evaluate the results.

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